

Appendix 1: Hairs collected using hair traps

This appendix contains photographs of five hair types collected in the hair tubes we deployed in Staten Island yards. The photographs presented here are of hair bases, tips, medullae, and cuticle patterns. We present a single representative photograph of each of these sections of hair for each species. Hairs were photographed at either 200X or 400X magnification using an echo revolve brightfield microscope.

Visual Identification	Figure number	Length (mm) (maximum, average)	Shaft width (nm) (range, average)	Medulla width (nm) (range, average)	Medullary index (range, average)	Medulla description	Medulla broad category
White-footed mouse (<i>Peromyscus sp.</i>)	1	15, 7.261	8-57, 26.16	6-41, 18.12	0.2143-1.0, 0.6878	Ovate aggregations 1-3 abreast, almost entire shaft width, aggregations can be fused	A, B, or F
Northern short tailed shrew (<i>Blarina brevicauda</i>)	2	10, 5.167	13-43, 23.56	6-27, 14.25	0.2558-0.7941, 0.6130	Wide, rectangular aggregations, never in multiple columns, almost entire shaft width	A or B
Eastern chipmunk (<i>Tamias striatus</i>)	3	10, 4.451	25-120, 74.42	8-97, 48.93	0.1481-0.9315, 0.6279	Dark column, 4-5 circular or ovular vacuolations abreast, almost entire shaft width -sometimes appears like ovate aggregations	A, B, D, E or F
Eastern meadow vole (<i>Microtus pennsylvanicus</i>)	4	9, 6.714	38-53, 45	30-46, 37.64	0.7143-0.9149, 0.8353	Ovate aggregations 3-4 abreast, almost entire shaft width, aggregations can be fused	A or F
Raccoon (<i>Procyon lotor</i>)	5	27, 7.239	10-157, 81.11	5-82, 31.83	0.1064-1.0, 0.3774	Homogenous, dark column half of shaft width or less; 1 column of square or rectangular aggregations if hair is exceptionally thin	B, D or E

Identified as *Peromyscus leucopus* (white-footed mouse)

Figure 1. A: Base of hair with follicle intact at 200X, B: Tip of hair at 200X, C: Medulla pattern of hair at 400X, D: Medulla pattern of hair at 400X, E: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X.

Identified as *Blarina brevicauda* (northern short-tailed shrew)

Figure 2. A: Base of hair with follicle intact at 200X, B: Medulla pattern of hair at 400X, C: Tip of hair at 200X, D: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X

Identified as *Tamias striatus* (chipmunk)

Figure 3.A: Base of hair with follicle intact at 200X, B: Tip of hair at 200X, C: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X – moonerized in inkscape software for better visibility, D: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X – moonerized in inkscape software for better visibility, E: Medulla pattern of hair at 400X

Identified as *Microtus pennsylvanicus* (meadow vole)

Figure 4. A: Base of hair with follicle intact at 200X, B: Tip of hair at 200X, C: Medulla pattern of hair at 400X, D: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X, E: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X – greyscale to improve visualization.

Identified as *Procyon lotor* (raccoon)

Figure 5. A: Base of hair with follicle intact at 200X, B: Medulla pattern of hair at 400X, C: Tip of hair at 200X, D: Cuticle scale pattern of hair at 200X